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Do bureaucratic and humanistic management practices influence organizational citizenship behavior?

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ABSTRACT

The study at Divine Word College of Laoag investigated how bureaucratic and humanistic management practices impact employees' organizational citizenship behavior. A thorough literature review bolstered the study's theoretical framework. Employing a descriptive and correlational design, the research surveyed the entire employee population. Validated questionnaires gathered data, analyzed through weighted mean and Pearson correlation coefficient (Pearson r). Results revealed a weak correlation between management practices and organizational citizenship behavior, urging future research to explore additional variables for a deeper understanding.

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Introduction

Different management styles significantly impact employees, as highlighted by several researchers. Towers (2017) noted that autocratic management affects motivation and productivity, while Wright (2018) expanded this to the overall workplace environment. Studies by Okon and Isong (2016), Stephen (2014), Jamal and Soomro (2011), Ingollan and Roussel (2017), Basit et al. (2017), and Asrar-ul-Haq and Kuchinke (2016) found correlations between various management styles and employee performance.

Building on these findings, this study posits that bureaucratic and humanistic management styles influence not only employee performance but also organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). Bureaucratic management, as described by Luenendonk (2020), is rule-based and limits individual initiative, focusing on efficiency and productivity. In contrast, humanistic management centers on human needs and values, balancing efficiency with a people-oriented

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approach (Pirson, 2017). Lucey (2017) and Thiruvankadam and Durairaj (2017) further noted that supportive management practices lead to positive behaviors that extend beyond job descriptions, benefiting the organization.

The current study aims to explore the correlation between bureaucratic and humanistic management styles and OCB. Employees have experienced varied management styles under different administrators, impacting their organizational behavior. This research seeks to determine the extent of these impacts on OCB.

The study encompasses an introduction discussing the rationale, theoretical background, and purpose; a literature review covering bureaucratic and humanistic management styles and OCB; a methodology section detailing research design, population, data gathering, ethical considerations, instruments, and statistical methods; an empirical data and analysis section presenting findings; and a results and discussion section leading to the conclusion.

The Review of Related Literature

Based on the concept of a literature review as a comprehensive summary of previous studies on a topic (Machi & McEvoy, 2016), this section explores the theories underpinning the current study. The review focuses on three key variables: autocratic management style, humanistic management style, and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) of employees. These variables form the theoretical foundation of the study, grounded in existing literature and previous research.

Bureaucratic Management style

The bureaucratic management style was proposed by Max Weber in 1947 in his book "Economy and Society," where he described bureaucracy as both the ideal and least ideal form of organization (Cleverism, n.d.). This style mandates adherence to specific rules, processes, and procedures, and obedience to the chain of command, emphasizing control over processes, people, inputs, and outputs (Management Study HQ, n.d.). Weber himself noted that bureaucracy can be dehumanizing, a point supported by Rudolph, Lloyd, and Rudolph Susanne (1979).

Bureaucracy aims to improve efficiency and productivity (Friedrich, 1990; Finer, 1941; Simon, 1947) but is characterized by highly structured, impersonal relationships (Hall, 1963). The Cambridge Dictionary reflects this dual nature, defining bureaucracy as both a system managed by many officials and one involving complicated, slow processes.

Originally intended for government, bureaucracy is now prevalent in private organizations, promoting efficiency but also slowing down service (Howard, 2012; Dwyer, 2009; Kersten, 2002; AmericanCatholic.org, 2013; Martin, 2010). Key characteristics of bureaucracy are hierarchy, formalization, and centralization (Quaisi, 2015). Hierarchy denotes different levels of authority (Millet, 1967), formalization involves rules regulating activities (Organ and Greene, 1981), and centralization means decisions are made by top authority, stifling innovation (Moch and Morse, 1977; Zmud, 1982; Editor et al., 2013).

Weber acknowledged bureaucracy's dual nature, arguing that excessive focus on rules and obedience can neglect the human aspect, leading to inefficiency and irrationality (Kang, 2005; Rose-Ackerman, 1986; Peter, 1993; Preston, 1987; Merton, 1952). Bureaucracy's rigidity dehumanizes workers, turning them into mechanistic technicians detached from their humanity and emotions (Bodley, 2002; Hummel, 2007). It overlooks informal organizational elements like relationships, leadership, and motivation, focusing solely on formal structures to achieve efficiency (Barnard, 1966).

Humanistic management style

The bureaucratic management style was proposed by Max Weber in 1947 in his book "Economy and Society," where he described bureaucracy as both the ideal and least ideal form of organization (Cleverism, n.d.). This style mandates adherence to specific rules, processes, and procedures, and obedience to the chain of command, emphasizing control over processes, people, inputs, and outputs (Management Study HQ, n.d.). Weber himself noted that bureaucracy can be dehumanizing, a point supported by Rudolph, Lloyd, and Rudolph Susanne (1979).

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Organizational Citizenship Behavior

One management objective is to foster employees' love for their workplace, as this dedication enhances organizational performance. This commitment is reflected in organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), which has been studied for over twenty years (Bateman & Organ, 1983). Research consistently shows that great organizations have employees who go beyond their job descriptions, contributing extra effort without expecting rewards (Organ, 1988, 1997; Podsakoff et al., 2000).

OCB, defined as behavior exceeding basic job responsibilities (Jahangir, 2004), is essential for achieving organizational goals (Bernard, 1938). It includes voluntary actions benefiting the organization, such as staying late to complete tasks (Organ, 1988, cited by Chiun Lo & Ramayah, 2009). This behavior is driven by values rather than rewards (Shamir, 1996).

Smith, Organ, and Near (1983) identified two OCB dimensions: altruism and generalized compliance. Altruism involves helping others voluntarily, while generalized compliance refers to conscientious behavior for its own sake, like punctuality. However, research has expanded these dimensions to five: conscientiousness, altruism, courtesy, sportsmanship, and civic virtue (Costa & McCrae, 1992). Civic virtue includes supporting organizational activities beyond job requirements (Deluga, 1998), while conscientiousness reflects dedication beyond required tasks (Kidder & Parks, 1993). Courtesy involves helping demoralized colleagues (Podsakoff et al., 2000), and sportsmanship entails tolerating job irritations, boosting group morale (Podsakoff & MacKenzie, 1997).

Fox and Spector (n.d.) simplify OCB into one dimension: altruistic behavior, encompassing acts that help coworkers and benefit the organization (OCBP and OCBO). This broad view covers various OCB aspects identified by other researchers.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: The conceptual framework illustrates the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. Independent variables are those that the researcher can manipulate, whereas dependent variables change in response to the independent variables (Salkind, 2010). This framework helps to understand how changes in the independent variables impact the dependent variables.

Statement of the Problems

The study determined the correlation between bureaucratic and humanistic management styles and organizational citizenship behavior. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What are the bureaucratic management practices of administrators of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region?
2. What are the humanistic management practices of administrators of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region?
3. What is the organizational citizenship behavior of employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region?
4. Is there a correlation between bureaucratic management style and organizational citizenship behavior?
5. Is there a correlation between humanistic management style and organizational citizenship behavior?

Assumption

The study operates under the assumption that management styles influence employees' organizational citizenship behavior to a certain extent. Additionally, it assumes that both bureaucratic and humanistic management styles, as well as organizational citizenship behavior, are quantifiable and measurable.

Hypothesis

Building on the findings of Lian and Tui (2012), which established a correlation between various leadership styles and organizational citizenship behavior, the present study hypothesizes that management styles similarly impact employees' organizational citizenship behavior.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study is focused solely on Divine Word Colleges within the Ilocos Region, narrowing its discussion to the impact of bureaucratic and humanistic management styles on employees' organizational citizenship behavior.

Research Methodology

Figure 1: The conceptual framework illustrates the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. Independent variables are those that the researcher can manipulate, whereas dependent variables change in response to the independent variables (Salkind, 2010). This framework helps to understand how changes in the independent variables impact the dependent variables.

Research Design of the Study

The study employed a descriptive assessment and correlational research design to evaluate the levels of bureaucratic and humanistic management styles among administrators of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region and their effect on organizational citizenship behavior. Ariola (2006) noted that descriptive correlation studies describe relationships among variables without establishing causality. Descriptive research aims to characterize a population, situation, or phenomenon, detailing profiles, frequency distributions, and the characteristics of people or situations. It answers questions such as what, when, how, and where, but not why (McCombes, 2020).

The Locale of the Study

The locale of the study was Divine Word Colleges namely Divine Word College of Laoag in Ilocos Norte and Divine Word College of Vigan in Ilocos Sur.

Population

The respondents of the study were the employees of these colleges. Given the limited number of employees, total enumeration sampling was employed, resulting in a sample size of 250 faculty and staff members.

Data gathering instruments

The study adapted validated questionnaires from Langer et al. (2019) for assessing a bureaucratic work environment and from Fox and Spector (n.d.) at Pennsylvania University and Chiun Lo and Ramayah (2009) for measuring organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). Specifically, the questionnaires from Fox and Spector were used to measure acts related to helping coworkers with job-related tasks (OCBP) and acts that benefit the organization (OCBO).

Data Gathering Procedures

To uphold the integrity of the investigation and ensure proper data collection procedures, the researcher first obtained permission from the college President to distribute the questionnaires within their respective institutions. During data collection, employees' representatives were tasked with retrieving data from individual employees before submitting it to the researcher.

Ethical Procedures

The study proceeded following thorough examination and approval by the research ethics committee, ensuring adherence to ethical standards and the preservation of human life and the environment.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To analyze the data, both descriptive and inferential statistics were employed. Specifically, the weighted mean was utilized to gauge the organizational climate levels within the schools, while the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was applied to assess the relationship between organizational climate and employee work engagement.

The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation will be used:

<i>Statistical Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
4.21-5.00	<i>strongly agree /Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree/High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>Somewhat agree/Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree/Low</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree/Very Low</i>

Empirical Data and Analysis

The data are presented below. The presentation follows the statement of the problems.

Problem 1: What are the bureaucratic management practices of administrators of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region?

Table 1: Bureaucratic Management Practices

Indicator	Mean	DI
Employees are always doing the same job and the same way every day	3.67	A/H
All employees are encouraged to follow the established rules and procedures	3.91	A/H
There is little action taken until a supervisor or the higher-up approves a decision.	3.78	A/H
Even small matters have to be referred to someone higher up for the final answer	3.69	A/H
In general, a person who wants to make his/her own decisions would be quickly discouraged	3.57	A/H
Employees are always monitored closely by their higher-up	3.73	A/H
Doing your job well means you have to follow the rules and procedures	3.70	A/H
Communications, decisions, and proceedings are put in writing for future references	3.83	A/H
Everyone has to conform to the rules and procedures because violation means punishment. 3 4 5	3.61	A/H
Overall Mean	3.72	A/H

Source: Langer, et.al. (2019)

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Interpretation
4.21-5.00	Strongly agree /Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree/High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree/Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree/Low
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree/Very Low

Bureaucratic practices received a composite mean of 3.72, signifying an "agree/high" rating. This suggests a bureaucratic environment characterized by consistency in job tasks, adherence to established rules, strict enforcement of protocols, respect for hierarchical structures, and close supervision. Abun et al. (2021) highlight that such an environment prioritizes efficiency over personal employee considerations, neglecting individual circumstances and needs. Ritzer (2004) critiques this approach, likening it to the dehumanizing effects of an "iron cage" governed by impersonal, rule-based control.

Problem 2: What are the humanistic management practices of administrators of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region?

Indicator	Mean	DI
The management puts the employees first before the work.	3.31	SWA/M
When making decisions, the management always considers the effect of the decision on the employees	3.31	SWA/M
The management considers the ideas of employees when making decisions	3.27	SWA/M
The management always tries their best to serve the needs of employees	3.23	SWA/M
The management listens to the employees when they employees counter problems in their work.	3.23	SWA/M
The management respect and treat the employees as human beings with dignity	3.25	SWA/M
The management recognizes the good efforts of the employees to help the institution	3.26	SWA/M
There is an open communication between employees and management	3.15	SWA/M
Overall Mean	3.25	SWA/M

Source: Salkind (2010).

The institutions' humanistic practices received a composite mean of 3.25, indicating a "somewhat agree/moderate" rating. This suggests that while the humanistic approach is not exceptionally high or low, it falls within a moderate range. Employees express partial agreement with aspects such as prioritizing employees over work, rewarding innovative ideas, considering employee input in decision-making, addressing employee needs and concerns, treating employees with dignity, and fostering open communication. Mele (2016) contends that humanistic management prioritizes human welfare and sees employees as essential contributors, fostering a positive work environment.

Problem 3: What is the organizational citizenship behavior of employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of OCBP and OCBO

Table 3: OCBP

Indicator	Mean	DI
OCBP		
Lent a compassionate ear when someone has a work problem	3.67	A/H
Lent a compassionate ear when someone has a personal problem	3.65	A/H
Change vacation schedules, work days, or shifts to accommodate co-workers' needs.	3.60	A/H
Help a less capable co-worker lift a heavy box or other objects	3.64	A/H
Went out of the way to give co-workers encouragement or express appreciation	3.65	A/H
Defended co-worker who was being 'put down' or spoken ill by other co-workers or supervisors	3.59	A/H
Help co-workers with personal matters such as sharing food or drinks	3.66	A/H
Lent money or personal property to a co-worker	3.71	A/H
Composite Mean	3.64	A/H

Source: Spector and Fox (2002)

Overall, the results indicate that employees' organizational citizenship behavior (OCBP) received a composite mean rating of 3.64, categorized as "agree/high". This suggests a consistently high level of OCBP, characterized by supportive actions towards colleagues such as offering emotional support, adjusting schedules to assist coworkers,

standing up for them in challenging situations, and sharing resources. Tran et al. (2018) argue that fostering strong workplace relationships can enhance employee commitment, reduce job stress, and improve performance. Sayankar (2015) underscores the importance of positive attitudes among employees, facilitating smoother communication and cooperation in the workplace.

Table 4: OCBO: Acts that direct toward the organization

OCBO		
Help new employees get oriented to the job	3.72	A/H
Offered suggestions to improve how work is done	3.75	A/H
Volunteered for extra work assignments	3.67	A/H
Said good things about your employer in front of others	3.77	A/H
Said good things about your school in the community outside the school	3.73	A/H
Give up meals and other breaks to complete the work	3.69	A/H
Offered suggestions for improving the work environment	3.77	A/H
came in early or stayed late without pay to complete a project or task	3.67	A/H
Composite Mean	3.72	A/H
Overall Mean	3.68	A/H

Source: Spector and Fox (2002)

Based on the table data, employees' organizational citizenship behavior (OCBO) towards the organization received a composite mean rating of 3.72, indicating an "agree/high" level. This suggests consistently high engagement in behaviors beneficial to the organization, such as assisting new colleagues, volunteering for additional tasks, advocating for the employer, prioritizing work over personal breaks, and exhibiting flexibility in work hours. Geue (2017) highlighted that positive workplace behavior fosters enhanced commitment and performance.

Problem 4: Is there a correlation between bureaucratic management style and organizational citizenship behavior?

Table 5: Bureaucratic and OCB

		Organizational Citizenship Behavior
Bureaucratic Management Style	Pearson Correlation	-.056
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.476

Analysis found no statistical significance in the relationship between bureaucratic management style and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) ($r = -0.056$, $p = 0.476$), suggesting that variations in OCB are not strongly associated with variations in bureaucratic management style. This implies that factors beyond bureaucratic management likely influence OCB. Therefore, organizations need a nuanced understanding of factors influencing positive workplace behaviors.

Relying solely on bureaucratic management may not suffice to foster desired OCB. A multifaceted strategy considering leadership, culture, and employee engagement is recommended. Additionally, a one-size-fits-all management approach is challenged; organizations should tailor strategies to their workforce and tasks for effective OCB cultivation.

Is there a correlation between humanistic management style and organizational citizenship behavior?

		Organizational Citizenship Behavior
Humanistic Management Style	Pearson Correlation	.044
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.594

The statistical analysis revealed a weak and non-significant positive correlation between humanistic management style and organizational citizenship behavior ($r = 0.044$, $p = 0.594$). This suggests that while there is a slight increase in organizational citizenship behavior with greater adoption of a humanistic management style, the correlation is minimal.

This subtle relationship underscores the need for a nuanced and context-specific management approach. Organizational citizenship behavior is influenced by various factors, advocating for a comprehensive strategy tailored to the organization's specific context.

Given the minimal strength of the correlation, relying solely on a humanistic management style may not significantly impact organizational citizenship behavior. Instead, organizations should adopt a holistic approach that integrates various management practices and considers their unique characteristics for optimal results.

Results and Discussion

Management endeavors to shape employees' workplace behavior to align with organizational objectives, recognizing the pivotal role of leadership and management style in this process (Mansor et al., 2012; Cakir & Adiguzel, 2020). This study examines the impact of bureaucratic and humanistic practices on employees' organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), particularly their interactions with coworkers and the organization. Results indicate a preference for bureaucratic over humanistic practices among administrators. While employees demonstrate high levels of OCB, the Pearson correlation reveals a weak positive association between bureaucratic/humanistic practices and OCB. This suggests that these management styles exert minimal influence on OCB, hinting at the presence of other individual and organizational factors shaping employee behavior.

Conclusion

The study investigated the impact of bureaucratic and humanistic practices on employees' organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). Findings reveal a moderate prevalence of bureaucratic practices compared to humanistic ones, while OCB among employees remains high. However, Pearson correlation analysis indicates a weak positive correlation between management practices and OCB, suggesting minimal influence. Other organizational factors likely contribute to OCB. Recognizing limitations due to the study's narrow scope, future research should encompass broader variables to measure employee OCB effectively.

Authors' Contribution.

Conceptualization: E.B.N., S.M.T., W.M.P., C.F.B. **Methodology:** E.B.N., S.M.T., W.M.P., C.F.B. **Data collection:** E.B.N., S.M.T., W.M.P., C.F.B. **Formal Analysis:** E.B.N., S.M.T., W.M.P., C.F.B.

All authors have read and agreed to the published final version of the manuscript

Institutional Review Board Statement: Ethical review and approval were waived for this study, due to the research does not deal with vulnerable groups or sensitive issues.

Data Availability Statement: the data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author. Data are not publicly available due to privacy.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest

References

- Abun, D., Calamaan, S.M.T., Magallanes, T., Encarnacion, M.J. & Sallong, M. (2021). Bureaucratic management style and workplace well-being of the Divine Word Colleges. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 10(3), 477-489.
- American Catholic. Org (2013). *Still a bureaucracy: normal paper works continues its flow at the Vatican*. Library of Congress. <https://www.americancatholic.org>
- Armandi, B., & Mills E.W. (1985). Bureaucratic and personalized strategies for efficiency and organization: an investigation of structures and efficiency in a set of 104 profit seeking firms. *American Journal of Economics and Sociology*, 44(3), 261- 277.
- Asrar-ul-Haq, M. & Kuchinke, P. k. (2016). Impact of leadership styles on employees' attitude towards their leader and performance: Empirical evidence from Pakistani Banks. *Future Business Journal*, 2(1), 54-64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fbj.2016.05.002>
- Basit, A., Sebastian, V. & Hassan, Z. (2017). Impact of leadership styles on employees' performance: a case study of a private organization in Malaysia. *International Journal of Accounting & Business Management*, 5 (2).
- Bateman, T.S. & D. W. Organ, D.W. (1983). Job satisfaction and the good soldier: the relationship between affect and employee "citizenship. *Academy of Management Journal*, 26, 587- 595.
- BBC (n.d). An end-in-itself. *Ethics Guide*. Retrieved April 02, 2024 from <http://www.bbc.co.uk>
- Bloemen, E. S. A. (1988). *Scientific management in Nederland, 1900-1930*. NEHA
- Barnard, C. I. (1966). *The Functions of executive*. Harvard University Press.
- Bodley, John H. (2002). *The Power of scale: a global history approach*. M.E. Sharpe
- Cakir, F. S. & Adiguzel, Z. (2020). Analysis of leader effectiveness in organization and knowledge sharing behavior on employees and organization. *SAGE Open*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244020914634>
- Chiun Lo, M. & Ramayah, T. (2009). The dimensionality of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) in a multicultural society: the case of Malaysia. *International Business Research*, 2(1).
- Cleverism (n.d). Understanding bureaucratic leadership. *Cleverism*. Retrieved March 15, 2024 from <https://www.cleverism.com>
- Dierksmeier, C. (2016). What is humanistic about humanistic management? *Humanist Management Journal*, 1, 9–32. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41463-016-0002-6>
- Derksen, M. (2014). Turning men into machines? Scientific management, industrial psychology & the 'human factor'. *Journal of the History of the Behavioral Sciences*, 50(2), 148-165. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jhbs.21650>
- Duncan, J. (1911). Efficiency -- real, unreal, and brutal. *American Federationist*, 18(5), 380–384.
- Dwyer, D. (2009). Victim of health insurance company "speak out". *ABC News*. <https://abcnews.go.com>
- Editor, D. Moynihan, P. & Wart, M. V. (2013). Lessons from leadership theory and the contemporary challenges of leaders. *Public Administration Review*, 73(4), 553–565.

- Faps, P.C. (2016). How poor workplace culture can affect well-being. *Psychopaedia*. Retrieved May 5, 2024 from <https://psychopaedia.org>
- Finer, H. (1941). Administrative responsibility in democratic government. *Public Administration Review*, 1, 335-350
- Fox, S., & Spector, P.E. (n.d). *Organizational Citizenship Behavior Checklist*. Unpublished paper. Loyola University of Chicago and University of South Florida.
- Friedrich, C. (1940). *Public policy and the nature of administrative responsibility*. In C. J. Friedrich (Ed.). *Public Policy*. Harvard University Press.
- Geue, P. (2017). Positive Practice in the Workplace: Impact on team climate, work engagement and task performance. *Emerging Leadership Journeys*, 1(10).
- Ghoshal, S. (2005). Bad management theories are destroying good management practices. *Academy of Management Learning & Education* 4(1), 75–91.
- Gompers, S. (1911b). The miracles of efficiency. *American Federationist*, 18(4), 273–279.
- Hall, R. H. (1963). The concept of bureaucracy: an empirical assessment. *American Journal of Sociology*, 69(1), 32-40.
- Harter, J. (2012). Unhealthy, stressed employees are hurting your business. *Gallup Business Journal*. Retrieved April 15, 2024 from <https://news.gallup.com>
- Howard, P.K. (2012). To Fix America's Education Bureaucracy, We Need to Destroy It. *The Atlantic*. Retrieved March 20, 2024 from <https://www.theatlantic.com>
- Hummel R (2007). *The bureaucratic experience: the postmodern challenge*, 5th edn. Routledge.
- ILO (2020). Workplace well-being. *International Labor Organization*. Retrieved May 05, 2024 from <https://www.ilo.org>
- Ingollan, D.N. & Roussel, J. (2017). Influence of leadership styles on employees' performance: a study of Turkana County, Kenya. *International Journal of Business and Social Science* 8(7).
- Jahangir, N., Akbar, M.M. & Haq, M. (2004). Organizational citizenship behavior: its nature and antecedents. *BRAC University Journal*, vol. 1(2), 75-85
- Jamal, S. & Soomro, A. (2011). Management styles and employees' performance: a study of public sector company. *South Asian Journal of Management Science*, 5(2), 65-71.
- Kang, H.S. (2005). Administrative discretion in the transparent bureaucracy. *Public Administration Quarterly*, 29(1), 162-185.
- Kerstein, S. (2019). Treating persons as means. *Stanford Encyclopedia of philosophy*. Retrieved May 15, 2024 from <https://plato.stanford.edu>
- Kersten, D. (2002). How to bend the rules of corporate bureaucracy. *USA TODAY*. Retrieved May 12, 2024 from <http://usatoday30.usatoday.com>

- Kidder, D. L. & Parks, M. J. (1993). The good soldier: Who is (s) he? *Academy of Management Best Papers Proceedings*, 363-367.
- Langer, J., Feeney, M.K., & Lee, S.E. (2019). Employee fit and job satisfaction in bureaucratic and entrepreneurial environments. *Review of Public Personnel Administration*, 39(1),135-155.
- Leedy, P.D. (1974). *Practical research: planning and design*. Macmillan.
- Lian, L.K. & Tui, L.G. (2012). Leadership styles and organizational citizenship behavior: the mediating effect of subordinates' competence and downward influence tactics. *Journal of Applied Business and Economics*, 13(2), 59 – 96.
- Lucey, P.A. (2017). *Leadership style and organizational citizenship behavior in community-based mental health facilities*. Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation. Walden University Press
- Luenendonk, M. (2020). *Bureaucratic Leadership Guide: Definitions, Qualities, Pros & Cons, Examples. Cleverism*. Retrieved May 01, 2024 from <https://www.cleverism.com>
- Lumen Principles of Management (n.d). Humanistic management. *Lumen Learning*. <https://courses.lumenlearning.com>
- Machi, L.A. & McEvoy, B.T. (2016). *The literature reviews*. Corwin, a SAGE Company.
- Kukreja, S. (n.d). Bureaucratic leadership guide: definitions, pros & cons, examples. *Management Study HQ*. Retrieved ma7 04, 2024 from <https://www.managementstudyhq.com>
- Mansor, A., Wai, N.N.C.M., Mohamed, A., & Shah, I. (2012). The relationship between management style and employees' well-being: a case of non-managerial staffs. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 40, 521-529. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.03.225>
- Martin, D. (2010). Gates criticizes bloated military bureaucracy. *ABC News*. Retrieved April 4, 2024 from <https://abcnews.go.com>
- McLeod, S. (2020). Humanistic approach. *Simply Psychology*. Retrieved April 15, 2024 from <https://www.simplypsychology.org>
- Mele, D. (2016). Understanding humanistic management. *Humanistic Management Journal*, 1, 33-55.
- Merton, R. (1952). *Bureaucratic Structure and Personality in Reader in Bureaucracy*. Free Press
- Millett, J. D. (1967). Enterprise-operations and administration: some notes on a systematic theory of organized endeavor. *Public Administration Review*, 27(5), 421- 428.
- Moch, M.K. & Morse, E.V. (1977). Size, centralization, and organizational adoption of innovations. *American Sociological Review*, 42(10), 716-725.
- Moorman, R., Niehoff, B.P. & Organ, D. (1993). Treating employees fairly and organizational citizenship behavior: Sorting the effects of job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and procedural justice. *Employees' Responsibilities and Rights Journal*, 6, 209–225. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01419445>.
- Münsterberg, H. (1913). *Psychology and industrial efficiency*. Houghton Mifflin.
- Neal, T. (2015). What is human dignity? *Open Access Library Journal*, 8(10).

- Ordever, R. (2018). Ignoring staff well-being will be at your peril. *Elite business*. Retrieved May 05, 2024 from <http://elitebusinessmagazine.co.uk>
- Podsakoff, P. M. & Mackenzie, S. B. (1997). The impact of organizational citizenship in organizational performance: Review and suggestion for future research. *Human Performance*, 10, 133-151.
- Hummel, R. (2007). The bureaucratic experience: the post-modern challenge. The 5th edition. *Library of Congress Cataloging-in-Publication Data*
- Moch, M. & Morse, E. (1977). Size, centralization, and organizational adoption of innovations. *American Sociological Review*, 42(5), 716-725.
- Okon, F.I. & Isong, E.U. (2016). Management styles and employees' performance in small scale business enterprises in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship Research*, 4(1), 51-61.
- Organ, D.W. (1997). Organizational citizenship behavior: it's constructed clean-up time. *Human Performance*, 10, 85-97 (1997).
- Organ, D.W. (1988). *Organizational citizenship behavior: The good soldier syndrome*. Lexington.
- Organ, D. & Greene, C. (1981). The Effects of formalization on professional involvement: a compensatory process approach. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 26(2), 237-252.
- Peters, B. G. (1993). Searching for a role: the civil service in American Democracy. *International Political Science Review*, 14(4), 373-386.
- Pirson, M (2017). Dignity and well-being as cornerstones of humanistic management. *Humanistic Management Association, Research Paper Series No. 17-9, Gabelli School of Business, Fordham University Research Paper No. 2916454*. SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2916454> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2916454>
- Pirson, M. (2017). What is humanistic management? *International Humanistic Management Association*. Retrieved May 07, 2024 from <http://humanisticmanagement.international>
- Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., Paine, J. B., & Bachrach, D. G. (2000). Organizational citizenship behaviors: A critical review of the theoretical and empirical literature and suggestions for future research. *Journal of Management*, 26, 513-563.
- Preston, L. M. (1987). Freedom and Bureaucracy. *American Journal of Political Science*, 31(4), 773-795.
- Quaisi, A. (2015). *The impact of bureaucracy characteristics on leadership*. Unpublished Dissertation: Missouri State University Press. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3527.6004>.
- Quested, E. & Duda, J.L. (2020). Exploring the social-environment determinants of well- and ill-being in dancers: a test of basic need. *Journal of Sport and Exercise Psychology*, 3(1).
- Rachels, J. (1985). *The idea of human dignity, in the elements of moral philosophy*. Random House, Inc.
- Ritzer, G. (2004). *Enchanting a disenchanted world: revolutionizing the means of consumptions*. Pine Forge Press.
- Rose-Ackerman, S. (1986). Reforming public bureaucracy through economic incentives? *Journal of Law, Economics, & Organization*, 2(1), 131-161.

- Rudolph, L. & Rudolph, S. (1979). Authority and power in bureaucratic and patrimonial administration: a revisionist interpretation of weber on bureaucracy. *World Politics*, 31(2), 195-227.
- Ryan, J. J. (2001). Moral reasoning as a determinant of organizational citizenship behaviors: A study in the public accounting profession. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 33, 233–244.
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2000). Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being. *American Psychologist*, 55, 68-78.
- Salkind, N.J. (2010). *Independent variable, in encyclopaedia of research design*. Sage Knowledge. <https://dx.doi.org/10.4135/9781412961288.n184>.
- Sayankar, V.N. (2015). Importance of employee's attitude in an organization. *Asian Journal of Management* 6(1), 33-36. <https://do.org/10.5958/2321-5763.2015.00006.2>
- Scott, W. D. (1911). *Increasing human efficiency in business: A contribution to the psychology of business*. Macmillan Press.
- Shamir, B. 1996. *Meaning, self, and motivation in organizations*. In R. M. Steers, L. W. Porter & G. A. Bigley (Eds.). *Motivation and leadership at work*: 149–165. McGraw-Hill.
- Singer, D. (n.d). 7 Ways to Master the Respect Effect in Employee Engagement. *Decision Wise*. Retrieved May 09, 2024 from <https://www.saba.com>
- Smith, C. A., Organ, D. W. & Near, J. P. (1983). Organizational citizenship behavior: Its nature and antecedents. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 68, 653-663.
- Simon H. (1946). *Administrative behavior*. Free Press.
- Stephen, D.L. (2014). *Effect of Management Styles on Employees' Performance: A Case Study of Norwegian People's Aid YEI Vocational Training Centre*. Unpublished Thesis. St. Lawrence University Press
- Thiruvankadam, T. & Durairaj, I.Y.A (2017). Organizational citizenship behavior: its definitions and dimensions. *GE-International Journal of Management Research*, 5(5).
- Towers. P. (2017). How different management styles affect employee motivation and productivity. *Task Pigeon*. Retrieved may 07, 2024 from <https://blog.taskpigeon.com>
- Tran, K. T., Nguyen, P. V., Dang, T. T. U., & Ton, T. N. B. (2018). The Impacts of the high-quality workplace relationships on job performance: a perspective on staff nurses in Vietnam. *Behavioral sciences (Basel, Switzerland)*, 8(12), 109. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs8120109>
- Van Dyne, L. L. C. & J. Parks, M. (1995). Extra role behaviors: in pursuit of construct and definitional clarity (a bridge over muddied waters). In L. L. Cummings & L. Van Dyne, J. Graham & R. M. Dienesch, (1994). Organizational citizenship behavior: construct redefinition, measurement, and validation. *Academy of Management Journal*, 37, 765-802.
- Von Kimakowitz, E., Pirson, M., Dierksmeier, C., & Spitzbeck, H. (2019). *Introduction to humanistic management in practice*. Working Paper. Fordham University Press.
- Wilkinson, D. (2000). *The researcher's toolkit*. Springer

Wright, J. (2018). How management styles affect the workplace. *Eagle's Flight*. Retrieved May 09, 2024 from <https://www.eaglesflight.com>

Zmud, R. (1982). Diffusion of modern software practices: influence of centralization and formalization. *Management Science*, 28(12), 1421-1431.

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